

PEDAGOGY IN THE TRADITION OF MENTOR-STUDENT: PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE

Kasimova J.

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884503>

Abstract. *The tradition of "mentor-student" is a long-standing value among our people, especially in all fields. This article discusses the important role of the mentor-student tradition, which is considered one of the ancient values, in the activities and lives of the young generation, young personnel, as well as the important aspects of the mentor-student tradition, especially pedagogy and education.*

Keywords: *teacher, student, education, tradition, spiritual heritage, pedagogical skill, talent, tradition, spirituality.*

*Knowledge and faith are a sword and a shield
Conclusion from the knowledge shared by scholars*

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale efforts are being made to further improve the education system, to inculcate national values and traditions in the content of teaching and upbringing, and to enrich them with advanced ideas. With the honor of independence, the priceless spiritual heritage created by our ancestors over the centuries, the restoration of forgotten values, and the realization of national identity are implemented at the level of the state program.

It is known that the formation, development and perfection of the human nature occurs only under the influence of systematic education. This painstaking process continues throughout life, that is, from the cradle to the grave.

Educational treatment is conditionally divided into two areas:

1. Education of morals and manners.

This means bringing the student to the world of enlightenment, culture and knowledge with the appropriate quality and competence.

After all, our scholars did not say for nothing: "Politeness is superior to knowledge".

2. The practice of instilling knowledge.

Of course, the value of science is in itself.

National education is closely related to the name of the nation and its history. Past cultural-pedagogical heritage and traditions serve as an important tool for youth education. The tradition of "Mentor-student" is important in the effective organization of national education in educational institutions. "Mentor-student" traditions - training of professional skills in young people, increasing their spiritual and educational potential, research, creativity, in a word, a unique educational effect in forming a mature person in all respects shows great importance. Another characteristic point is that as a result of its use, the learner develops confidence in his own abilities, correct assessment of the situation, and willful qualities, besides, student's social activity is under the control of the teachers. The greatest duty of a teacher is to train intelligent, smart and capable students who can contribute to the development of the country. In order to train a good student, a teacher must first of all have professional potential, moral maturity, broad outlook and common sense.

In the ancient tradition of mentor-apprenticeship, the mentor not only gives guidance and instructions to his students, but also prepares them for independent activities and passes on work experience, knowledge and skills from generation to generation.

The following pedagogical principles are important in the mentor-student tradition:

- awareness and activity, i.e. to fully understand the specific aspects and essence of one or another activity, to act actively towards its prospects and development;
- thoroughness in mentoring the secrets of science;
- taking into account the close connection between education and life;
- taking into account the connection between theoretical knowledge and practice in guiding independence and creative research;
- the content of teaching, education and stages of apprenticeship should have a clear and logical order;
- taking into account the student's age and unique characteristics.

Therefore, the use of the tradition of "mentor-student" in the continuous education system gives the intended effect. According to the ideas of pedagogical theory, practical skills and qualifications are formed directly through continuous work on oneself. The tradition of "mentor-student" is important because it creates creative research in pupils, students, young people and young pedagogues, takes into account their individual characteristics in the process of pedagogical activity, and creates favorable conditions for the further development of the student's talent. Such situations inculcate in young people not only a responsible approach to their profession, but also spiritual and moral qualities such as respect for elders, loyalty to their profession, respect for national values. In the upbringing of a child, following the customs, traditions, and rules of ethics of the ancient ancestors, special attention should be paid to the effective use of the national education system of our people, and teachers should not spare their strength and intelligence in this regard.

There are unwritten laws in life, but if they are not followed, they can lead to ugly consequences. One of these is the mentor-student relationship. The manners, values, and conditions of communication among the people have been living, maturing and developing since ancient times in the form of such unwritten laws. There is no profession that has not matured under a mentor. The bond between mentor and disciple is very delicate and can be broken by the slightest movement, and even when connected, a knot can remain. In order to prevent such a situation from happening, first of all, the student must have unlimited love for his teacher, trust him, understand his every word and behavior, and follow him. It is customary for a student to complete what he has learned from his teacher, to please his teacher and receive his blessing before starting independent work. The students who did not receive a blessing did not have a bowl, not one or two. Consent is to ensure happiness. Only a teacher who is satisfied with his student gives him a blessing from the heart. It is not for nothing that our people created the wise saying "A disciple who has not seen a teacher - blankets for every status".

In fact, no matter what field he is in, a student who does not have a mentor may not know the procedures, etiquette, and special direction of that field. This can cause a number of problems in the course of its activity.

In the Eastern nations, respect for science teachers and teachers is instilled in the minds of children. In the framework of Eastern etiquette, honoring the teacher as one's own father,

respecting him, the teacher, in turn, seeing his student as his own child and teaching him the secrets of his craft or profession, as well as upbringing and manners taught a lesson.

"In particular, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, a subtle writer, an accurate scholar, one of the 15th century enlighteners, said: "He who replaces the respect of teachers and teachers will find happiness both in this world and in the hereafter." had written. According to him, four things are proof of happiness: the right word, humility, work in an honest profession, keeping a secret. That is, learning a profession or teaching a trade is hard work, which is central to the views of the scientist."¹

Koshifi also touched on the conditions of mentorship and said: "I know that no work can be done without a mentor, and whoever does something without a mentor, the foundation of that work should not be strong." Whoever starts work without a mentor, his work and actions will not be fruitful, follow the mentor and be happy, serve the mentor for a while, then become a mentor yourself... If they ask who is a perfect person, he is say that he is a pure sectarian, a wise and refined person who sees his faults. There is no trace of envy, grudge or greed in him."

The famous philosopher and thinker, scholar of encyclopedic sciences Abu Nasr al-Farabi (873-930) makes such a demand for a teacher-mentor: A teacher should neither oppress his students nor indulge them too much². Because too much tyranny makes the student hate the teacher, and if the teacher is too soft, the student will despise him and may even become cold from the knowledge he imparts. We know from historical sources that the scholar and statesman Mirzo Ulugbek, who lived and worked in the 15th century, founded the tradition of mentor-student and made a great contribution to the development of this school. The teacher repeatedly emphasizes the importance of never oppressing his student, but on the contrary, of helping him, and of sincere cooperation between them.

The tradition of "mentor-student" has been going on for a long time, especially in the field of art, compared to other fields. Each artist, entering the path of art, first of all goes to a mentor in the direction he chooses. He learns the secrets of art, knowledge and skills from him. The teacher works hard for his student to become a mature artist in the future.

It is known that the experience of the mentor-student tradition, which has an educational impact on future specialist teachers in higher educational institutions, is expressed as a practically proven factor. As a result of the rapid scientific and technical development process, the aspects of the educational process are being perfected, new pedagogical technologies and innovative methods are introduced into their system in a wide range of cases, it is necessary to pay attention to issues such as determining the professional relevance of future specialists, helping them in time, mentoring makes it necessary to make appropriate use of the traditions of discipleship. Based on it, the issues of bringing up a well-rounded generation find their expression.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that today, the need to speed up the attention to the comprehensive formation of young specialists has become the need of the hour, and they are being focused on increasing their professional activity. Forms of conveying accumulated experiences to the minds of young people are also changing due to changes in historical conditions.

Due to the honor of independence, one of the main tasks of the further development of the mentor-student tradition is the establishment of a new educational system that will become the basis for the development of independent Uzbekistan. The Law "On Education" and the National

Personnel Training Program, adopted at the IX session of Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997, serves as the legal basis for its implementation.

REFERENCES

1. D. Malikova. Sharq mamlakatlarida “ustoz-shogird”lik an’alarining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi. Maqola. Science and Education” Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 April 2022
2. Mahkamov U., Tilyaboeva N. Kasbiy mahorat. / O’quv qo’llanma. - T.: TDIU, 2007.
3. O’.Q Tolipov. “Ustoz - shogirdlik qadriyatlari”-risola; Toshkent: “Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU”- 2015.